

A double two-sources energy-water balance model for improving evapotranspiration estimates and irrigation management in fruit trees fields

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ABSTRACT

Improving the use of water in irrigated agriculture is meaningful in a period of increasing water scarcity conditions. A more accurate estimate of evapotranspiration (ET) and its components thus becomes fundamental to better quantify the irrigation water volumes. Many existing models, based on different remote sensing data, provide daily estimates of latent heat flux (LE) from correlation between net radiation and instantaneous estimates of LE, computed as residual component of the energy balance equation or from a correlation of land surface temperature (LST) with vegetation indices. However, they mainly lack of solutions which are continuous in time (e.g. hourly), independent from satellite LST availability and a simultaneous estimation of soil moisture. Addressing this gap, a double two-sources energy-water balance model (FEST-2×2-EWB) is developed based on the decoupling of both water and energy fluxes between the bare soil or grass interrow and the trees rows. This novel parameterization approach enables the differentiation of water uptake from the root zone, which varies between tall trees and grass, considering the dynamics of soil moisture (SM) in the superficial and deep layers. Additionally, it provides partitioned values for transpiration and evaporation. The new model has been evaluated in two irrigated trees fields in the North of Italy, a walnut trees field from 2019 to 2021 and a pear trees field, for the year 2022. Results of the study showcased a root-mean-square-error (RMSE) of about 55 W m^{-2} and a bias of about 40 W m^{-2} for hourly latent and sensible heat fluxes when compared to the eddy covariance stations located in the fields, while a RMSE of $2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (bias of $1.5 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for LST and of 0.04 for SM. The FEST-2×2-EWB model significantly enhances the accuracy of ET simulation in fruits trees areas in respect to the original one source and one-layer version of the same model. Finally, the application of an irrigation optimization strategy with this new model, allowed to demonstrate its potentiality in water saving (about 90 mm in a year) in respect to farmers applied irrigation, and with a difference of about 60 mm between using the double two-sources model and single source one.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is the largest water user with about 70% of total fresh-water consumption with peaks of 80% in the Mediterranean area (Zucaro, 2014; FAO, 2018), which is projected to further increase due to climate change, population growth but also more demanding lifestyles and diets (Ingram, 2011; Wada et al., 2011). However, the irrigation sector is the one with the largest differences between modern technologies and largely diffused ancient traditional practices (Singh and Singh, 2017). Thus, improving irrigation water use efficiency is nowadays a fundamental step for achieving sustainable food and water, security and safety (Alexandratos and Bruinsma, 2012).

The integration of agro-hydrological modelling with remote sensing

and ground data has been used to improve the estimates of crop water needs and evapotranspiration, and thus to help to define precise irrigation volumes distribution over time and space (D'Urso, 2010; Calera Belmonte et al., 2017; Bastiaanssen et al., 2000; Prueger et al., 2018; Knipper et al., 2019; Corbari et al., 2019; Corbari and Mancini, 2022).

A way of estimating crop water needs is based on the use of energy balance models based on satellite land surface temperature (LST), which directly regulates the evaporative fluxes (Allen et al., 2015; Anderson et al., 2020; Guzinski et al., 2020). The most diffused approaches are the residual models, where usually the latent heat flux (LE) is computed from the closure of the energy budget equation. These could be based on a single source approach where total fluxes are computed for a homogeneous pixel (Bastiaanssen et al., 1998; Su, 2002) or a two-sources

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scheme where evaporation and transpiration are computed separately considering the heterogeneity of the pixel (Norman et al., 1995; Anderson et al., 1997).

These models are heavily dependent on satellite LST data availability limited by clouds and satellite revisit time and also data spatial resolution. However, hydrological models (Corbari et al., 2020; Kustas and Prueger, 2008) overcome these limitations, but usually require many information on soil hydraulic parameters as well as on irrigation volumes which are often difficult to obtain. These models are able to compute continuously in time SM profiles, LST and evapotranspiration independently from satellite data, while, simultaneously, exploiting remote-sensing data, when available, to enhance and correct the prognostic model output. In fact, satellite data of LST are usually used for parameters calibration (Corbari and Mancini, 2014; Crow et al., 2003) or for data assimilation (Crow and Wood, 2003). An example is the FEST-EWB (Flash-flood Event-based Spatially-distributed rainfall-runoff Transformation Energy-Water Balance) hydrological model, which computes LST as an internal variable and has physically-based, non-residual formulations for the components of the energy balance (Corbari et al., 2011).

However, these models have limitations in heterogeneous areas, such as vineyards or fruit trees, where bare soil or grass coexist with rows of tall plants with very different phenological characteristics leading to an unbalanced partitioning between the latent and sensible heat fluxes and inaccuracies in the representation of the evapotranspiration process (Fisher et al., 2008; Norman et al., 1995; Burchard-Levine et al., 2022; Andreu et al., 2018). A limited number of these models based on the system of energy-water balance are available in literature, especially with a two-sources scheme (Cui and Jia, 2021).

The accuracy of all these types of models is usually quantified by comparison with ET estimates from eddy-covariance (EC) stations (Baldochi et al., 2001; Baldochi, 2020), even though the measured energy budget at these stations is almost always not closed (Wilson et al., 2002; Masseroni et al., 2014). As a result, correction methods have been developed over the years mostly based on the idea of LE underestimation (Twine et al., 2000). Moreover, methods for partitioning the total evapotranspiration into evaporation (E) and transpiration (T) have been developed, even though many limitations and uncertainties are still present (Nelson et al., 2020; Perez-Priego et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2016; Scott and Biederman, 2017; Scanlon and Kustas, 2012).

Thus, to overcome all these limitations, a new version of the FEST-EWB model (Corbari et al., 2011) is proposed, the FEST-2×2-EWB model (Flash-flood Event-based Spatially-distributed rainfall-runoff Transformation 2×2-sources Energy-Water Balance) based on the decoupling of fluxes between the bare soil or grass interrow and the trees rows. The two-sources scheme is thus developed for representing the crop and soil processes both in the water and the energy balances. This also allows diversifying the water uptake from the root zone which differ for tall trees from grass. The model is thus able to provide continuously in time and distributed in space estimates of the total evapotranspiration flux as well as the partitioned transpiration and evaporation and of the soil moisture dynamic for the superficial and deep layers considering the crop and soil components.

The model has been implemented and verified in two irrigated tree fields in the North of Italy: a drip-irrigated walnut trees field, from 2019 to 2021, and a micro-sprinkler irrigated pear trees field, for the year 2022. In both fields, eddy covariance measurements are available from dedicated monitoring campaigns. In addition, the original FEST-EWB (Corbari et al., 2011) and the FEST-2-EWB (Paciolla et al., 2023) models were also compared against FEST-2×2-EWB simulations.

Finally, an irrigation optimization strategy based on soil moisture stress thresholds (Allen et al., 1998; Corbari and Mancini, 2022) has been applied to the different versions of the FEST-EWB model, to quantify not only the potential water saving in respect to the actual applied irrigation by the farmer, but also to understand which model version could better contribute to irrigation management.

This paper will thus allow to fill the existing research gaps for continuous in time ET estimates over heterogeneous areas by: 1) developing an integrated two source model that computes continuously in time (1 h) and distributed in space (10 m) either the evapotranspiration and the soil moisture dynamics; 2) computing the LST which could be used for calibrating and/or validating the model parameters by comparison with satellite observed LST data; 3) demonstrating the ability of the newly implemented model to improve irrigation management in tree crops.

2. Material and methods

2.1. The double two sources energy-water balance model structure

The FEST-2 × 2-EWB model is a four components energy-water balance model, based on a double two sources scheme, which simulates continuously in time and distributed in space the energy and water balances for a vegetated part (“canopy”, c) and a non-vegetated one (“soil”, s) in which the pixel unit is divided, depending on the global pixel vegetation fraction (f_v). Each sub-area is then characterised further by differentiating the soil into two layers, a thin and shallow one (where water exchanges and storage are quick) and a thicker and deeper one (with slower water dynamics and where most plant root systems extract the water that fuels the transpiration processes). Thus, this model requires the solution of four water balance equations and two energy balance equations for each pixel.

In using this intra-pixel pattern, the model energy balance structure can be classified as “patch/uncoupled” (PU), meaning that the pixel sub-areas are energetically independent of each other and interact solely with the atmosphere through their own energy balance (Lhomme et al., 2012). From the perspective of the water balance, the model can also be classified as PU (as no horizontal sub-pixel water transfer occurs), but each pixel sub-area, being divided in a superficial and deep soil layer, works with a “layered/coupled” (LC) structure. This scheme, frequently associated with two-source energetical models (e.g., the TSEB model), identifies a horizontal partition, where the lower and upper layers influence each other (e.g., the percolation of the superficial layer becomes a water input for the deeper one).

The FEST-2×2-EWB model represents an evolution of the FEST-EWB model. Its original formulation is based on the system of the energy and water budget equations in each pixel of the analyzed area, searching for the representative equilibrium temperature (RET), defined as the land surface temperature that guarantees closure of the energy balance equation. The energy and water balances equations are then connected by the evapotranspiration flux. A detailed description of the FEST-EWB model is reported in Corbari et al. (2011). FEST-EWB has been demonstrated to be able to simulate ET and SM at local scale against eddy covariance stations measurements as well as at Irrigation Consortium scale in comparison to satellite land surface temperature (LST) data considering also irrigation distribution (Corbari et al., 2013; Corbari et al., 2020; Paciolla et al., 2021). FEST-EWB has also been used for smart irrigation management combined with remote sensing data and also meteorological forecast (Corbari et al., 2019; Corbari and Mancini, 2022). Recently, an improvement has been developed by introducing a two-sources energy budget scheme for crop and bare soil mixed pixels, FEST-2-EWB (Paciolla et al., 2023), although this version of the model is still limited by a single water balance equation representing a vertically and horizontally heterogeneous pixel.

For each entire pixel (i.e., without considering the vegetation partitioning), the FEST-2 × 2-EWB model resolves a system of three equations: two for the water balances of the superficial and deep layers, and one for the energy balance.

Fig. 1. FEST-2 × 2-EWB model structure: where SM , $SM_{(1)}$ and $SM_{(2)}$ refer to the soil moisture of the total, superficial and deep layers, respectively, P to the precipitation rate, I to irrigation, Pe to the drainage flux, Pe_1 to the drainage flux from the shallow layer to the deeper one, while Pe_2 from the deeper one, ET to the evapotranspiration, Δz is the total soil depth, Δz_1 is the superficial soil depth (m) and Δz_2 the deep soil depth (m), C_1 is the capillary rise between the two layers and the groundwater table, Rn ($W m^{-2}$) is the net radiation, G ($W m^{-2}$) is the soil heat flux, H ($W m^{-2}$) is the sensible heat flux, while LE ($W m^{-2}$) is the latent heat flux. Subscript c is for the canopy component and s for the soil one. f_v is the global pixel vegetation fraction.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial SM_{(1)}}{\partial t} \cdot \Delta z_1 = P + I + C_{(1)} - Pe_{(1)} - \beta ET \\ \frac{\partial SM_{(2)}}{\partial t} \cdot \Delta z_2 = Pe_{(1)} + C_{(2)} - C_{(1)} - Pe_{(2)} - \delta ET \\ Rn - G - H - LE = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $SM_{(1)}$ and $SM_{(2)}$ refer to the soil moisture of the superficial and deep layers, respectively (-), P to the precipitation rate ($mm h^{-1}$), I to irrigation ($mm h^{-1}$), Pe_1 to the drainage flux from the shallow layer to the deeper one ($mm h^{-1}$), while Pe_2 from the deeper one ($mm h^{-1}$), ET to the evapotranspiration ($mm h^{-1}$), Δz_1 is the superficial soil depth (m) and Δz_2 the deep soil depth (m), C_1 is the capillary rise between the two layers ($mm h^{-1}$) and C_2 between the deep layer and the groundwater table ($mm h^{-1}$), Rn ($W m^{-2}$) is the net radiation, G ($W m^{-2}$) is the soil heat flux, H ($W m^{-2}$) is the sensible heat flux, while LE ($W m^{-2}$) is the latent heat flux. The total evapotranspiration from the soil layers is partitioned into the shallow-layer (ET_1) and the deep-layer (ET_2) components:

$$ET_1 = \beta \cdot ET, ET_2 = \delta \cdot ET \quad (2)$$

$$\beta + \delta = 1 \quad (3)$$

where β and δ represent the partition coefficients which identify the contribution of each layer to the total ET flux. This structure stems from the assumption that the evapotranspiration process takes place in both layers of the soil, although it originates mainly in the deep layer, as the one where there is the greatest root density.

2.1.1. Energy balance

The structure of the energy balance is designed so that its closure is verified both at a pixel-fraction scale and at global scale. For each pixel, the crop and soil parts are considered in independent thermal equilibrium with their own soil/crop and atmospheric layers, allowing to write two separate energy balances for two “virtual” pixels: one completely bare ($f_v=0$) and the other fully covered with vegetation ($f_v=1$). This

means that the superficial temperatures at which these equilibria are reached are separate for the two sub-areas, and are identified as the soil temperature (T_s) and the crop temperature (T_c). The two equations are:

$$\begin{cases} Rn_s - G_s = LE_s + H_s \\ Rn_c - G_c = LE_c + H_c \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where the first equation depends on the soil land surface temperature, which is the temperature that closes the energy balance for the non-vegetated cell sub-area, while the second refers to the vegetated part of the pixel and so depends on the crop land surface temperature, the temperature that closes the energy balance for the vegetated cell sub-area.

The terms of the soil energy balance equation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} Rn_s = R_{sin}(1 - \alpha) + \xi_a \sigma T_a^4 - \xi_s \sigma T_s^4 \\ G_s = \left(\frac{g_{therm}}{\Delta z} \right) (T_s - T_{zero}) \\ H_s = \frac{\rho_a c_p}{r_{abs}} (T_s - T_a) \\ LE_s = \frac{\rho_a c_p}{\gamma(r_{abs} + r_s)} (e^*(T_s) - e_a) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where γ is psychrometric constant ($Pa^\circ C^{-1}$), e^* is the saturation vapour pressure (Pa) computed as a function of the T_s and e_a is the vapour pressure (Pa), c_p is the air specific heat ($kJ kg^{-1}^\circ C^{-1}$), ρ_a is the humid air density ($kg m^{-3}$), r_{abs} is the aerodynamic resistance ($s m^{-1}$) referred to the soil (Thom, 1975). The soil thermal conductivity (g_{therm}) is a function of $SM_{(1)s}$, the soil moisture of the superficial layer of the bare soil part. Finally, α is the albedo (-), ξ_a the atmospheric emissivity (-), σ the Stefan-Boltzmann constant ($W m^{-2} K^{-4}$), ξ_s the bare soil emissivity (-), and the soil resistance, r_s ($s m^{-1}$), is formulated at the evaporating soil surface (Sun, 1982):

$$r_s = 3.5 \left(\frac{\theta_{sat}}{SM_{(1)s}} \right)^{2.3} + 33.5 \quad (6)$$

where θ_{sat} is the soil moisture value at saturation.

The equations describing the energy fluxes of the vegetated area can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} Rn_c = R_{sin}(1 - \alpha) + \xi_a \sigma T_a^4 - \xi_c \sigma T_c^4 \\ G_c = \left(\frac{g_{term}}{\Delta z} \right) (T_c - T_{zero}) \\ H_c = \frac{\rho_a c_p}{r_a} (T_c - T_a) \\ LE_c = \frac{\rho_a c_p}{\gamma(r_a + r_c)} (e^*(T_c) - e_a) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with the main symbols retaining the meaning of the previous Eq. 4. In this case, the soil thermal conductivity is formulated as a function of $SM_{(1)c}$, that is the soil moisture value of the superficial layer of the vegetated part. Finally, ξ_c is the crop emissivity (-), r_a the aerodynamic resistance ($s\ m^{-1}$) referred to the crop, and r_c ($s\ m^{-1}$) the canopy resistance, which describes the resistance of vapour flow through the transpiring crop, expressed as (Jarvis, 1976):

$$r_c = \frac{r_{smin} (FC - WP)}{LAI (SM_{2,c} - WP)} \quad (8)$$

In which r_{smin} is the minimum stomatal resistance ($s\ m^{-1}$), LAI the leaf area index, $SM_{(2)c}$ the soil moisture value of the deeper layer of the vegetated part, FC the field capacity ($m^3\ m^{-3}$) and WP the wilting point ($m^3\ m^{-3}$). As the main water evaporation in a vegetated pixel is associated to the plant activity, which is conditioned by the water availability at root level, the canopy resistance is conditioned to the deep-layer soil moisture value.

Finally, the global energy fluxes are obtained from the combination of the fluxes pertaining to each virtual pixel, weighted on f_v . It is possible to express their computation for any given cell, as:

$$\begin{cases} Rn = (1 - f_v) \bullet Rn_s + f_v \bullet Rn_c \\ G = (1 - f_v) \bullet G_s + f_v \bullet G_c \\ H = (1 - f_v) \bullet H_s + f_v \bullet H_c \\ LE = (1 - f_v) \bullet LE_s + f_v \bullet LE_c \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Assuming blackbody emissivity, a pixel global LST is obtained from the two sub-pixel temperatures between soil (T_s) and crop (T_c) deriving it from the outgoing long-wave radiation balance, as follows (Norman et al., 1995):

$$RET^4 \cong (1 - f_v) \bullet T_s^4 + f_v \bullet T_c^4 \quad (10)$$

The overall pixel surface temperature is identified as a Representative Equilibrium Temperature (RET), in analogy to its definition in the original FEST-EWB model. In FEST-EWB, RET is the temperature that closes the energy balance for the overall pixel, whereas the FEST-2 \times 2-EWB RET is the representative radiative temperature for the pixel, obtained from a combination of the two fraction-level temperatures (T_s and T_c) that actually close the single (and separate) energy balances for their respective pixel sub-areas.

2.1.2. Water balance

As for the energy balance, the water balances are solved separately for the crop and soil parts of each pixel. For each part, two equations are written to represent the water fluxes dynamic in the shallower superficial layer Δz_1 and in the deeper one Δz_2 . The irrigation volume (I) is entirely provided to the crop part of the pixel, while the precipitation flux is partitioned according to the respective fractional area, expressed in f_v .

For the crop sub-area, the system can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial SM_{(1)c}}{\partial t} \bullet \Delta z_1 = f_v \bullet P + I + C_{1,c} - Pe_{1,c} - \beta \quad ET_{crop} \\ \frac{\partial SM_{(2)c}}{\partial t} \bullet \Delta z_2 = Pe_{1,c} + C_{2,c} - C_{1,c} - Pe_{2,c} - \delta \quad ET_{crop} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Where $SM_{(1)c}$ and $SM_{(2)c}$ refer to the superficial and deep soil moisture of the crop and ET_{crop} identifies the global crop evapotranspiration.

The infiltration is modeled according to a modified version of the SCS-CN method (Ravazzani et al., 2007), the percolation flux following Brooks and Corey (1966), while the drainage flux (Eagleson, 1978).

Similarly, for the bare soil subpixel, the water balance system could be written as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial SM_{(1)s}}{\partial t} \bullet \Delta z_1 = (1 - f_v)P + C_{1,s} - Pe_{1,s} - \quad ET_s \\ \frac{\partial SM_{(2)s}}{\partial t} \bullet \Delta z_2 = Pe_{1,s} + C_{2,s} - C_{1,s} - Pe_{2,s} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where $SM_{(1)s}$ and $SM_{(2)s}$ refer to the superficial and deep soil moisture of the bare soil, and ET_s to the bare soil evaporation.

Globally, the water fluxes are obtained from the sum of the fraction fluxes weighted on f_v , for each cell as:

$$\begin{cases} SM_1 = (1 - f_v) \bullet SM_{1,s} + f_v \bullet SM_{1,c} \\ SM_2 = (1 - f_v) \bullet SM_{2,s} + f_v \bullet SM_{2,c} \\ Pe_1 = (1 - f_v) \bullet Pe_{1,s} + f_v \bullet Pe_{1,c} \\ Pe_2 = (1 - f_v) \bullet Pe_{2,s} + f_v \bullet Pe_{2,c} \\ C_1 = (1 - f_v) \bullet C_{1,s} + f_v \bullet C_{1,c} \\ C_2 = (1 - f_v) \bullet C_{2,s} + f_v \bullet C_{2,c} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

2.2. Irrigation optimization

The optimization of the irrigation volume and timing is based on the idea of keeping the soil moisture value in between the field capacity and a crop stress threshold (SM_{STRESS}), below which the crops start to suffer water stress (Allen et al., 1998). Thus, irrigation volume and timing could be controlled, and irrigation volumes as well as drainage flux (e.g. no overpass of field capacity) are reduced.

Allen et al. (1998) defined the SM_{STRESS} as a function of crop and soil types as well as climate as follows:

$$SM_{STRESS} = FC - p \bullet (FC - WP) \quad (14)$$

where p is the soil moisture depletion ratio between the readily available water (RAW) and the total available water (TAW). p should then be corrected (p_{cor}) for the local climate, according to Allen et al. (1998).

This optimization scheme is implemented into both the FEST-2 \times 2-EWB model and the original FEST-EWB one, which are thus run without considering the observed irrigation as input variable.

The different irrigation scenarios (e.g. observed irrigation and optimized irrigation) will be evaluated using some performance indicators (Table 1) which consider the impact of a different irrigation volume on the crop yield, evapotranspiration and percolation.

2.3. Case studies description and data

Two study cases of fruit trees have been selected in Central Italy (Fig. 2).

The first one is a walnut trees field located in central Italy in the Emilia-Romagna Region near the city of Forlì (Fig. 2), with a humid subtropical climate with Mediterranean features, characterized by warm and wet winters, while summers are hot and dry with nut production that relies almost completely on irrigation. The mean annual

Table 1

Water performance indicators employed in this study.

Indicators	Formula
Crop water productivity (WPC)	
	$WPC \left[\frac{kg}{m^3} \right] = \frac{Yield}{ET} \quad (15)$
Irrigation water productivity (WPI)	
	$WPI \left[\frac{kg}{m^3} \right] = \frac{Yield}{Irrig.} \quad (16)$
Percolation deficit (PD)	
	$PD [-] = 1 - \frac{Perc.}{Rain + Irrig.} \quad (17)$
Irrigation efficiency (IE)	
	$IE [-] = \frac{ET}{Rain + Irrig.} \quad (18)$

temperature is around 14 °C, while precipitation is regularly distributed along the year with an annual mean of about 761 mm.

The analysed field covers an area of about 38 ha where the Chandler variety of walnuts are cultivated. Walnut trees present on the farm are relatively young so they have a height around 10 m. The walnut-trees spacing is about 5 m, with the interrow mainly covered with grass. The main roots' density distribution is located around 60 cm depth. The soil texture of the analyzed field is predominantly silt loam. The trees are drip irrigated, with the Consorzio Emiliano Romagnolo (CER) who provides suggestions to optimize irrigation. The dates of the irrigation events and the water volumes are known. The walnuts are usually harvested at the beginning of September.

The experimental field has been monitored from 2019 to 2021 with an eddy covariance station (Corbari et al., 2023), allowing to measure the main component of the energy and water balances, as the net radiation and the ground heat flux, as well as evapotranspiration and soil

moisture dynamics. The turbulent fluxes have been estimated through the PEC software (Polimi Eddy Covariance) (Corbari et al., 2012) following the standard correction procedures (Foken, 2008). Finally, to account for the traditional non-closure of the energy balance, the latent and sensible heat fluxes have been corrected for their underestimation applying a methodology based on the preservation of the Bowen-ratio (Twine et al., 2000) method to reach the energy budget closure.

Soil moisture probes are installed at different soil depths from 10 cm to 50 cm, which are representative of the maximum density of crops roots. Station characteristics and data analysis are described in Corbari et al. (2023).

The second case study is also located within the Emilia-Romagna region, near the town of Vignola (Modena): a pear tree field farm, within the Burana irrigation consortium (lower row of Fig. 2).

The field is 1.08 ha wide, and features trees of different age, generally 2.5–3.5 m high and organized in rows 3 m apart (resulting in a 1111 plants/ha density). It has been monitored with an eddy covariance station installed in May 2022 and removed in October 2022 (the data are analyzed with the same procedure for the walnut trees field. In addition, four soil moisture sensors have been installed (5TM sensor METER) at different soil depths: three along the tree line (10 cm, 30 cm and 55 cm depth) and one in the grass-covered inter-row (10 cm depth). The trees are irrigated via sprinkler irrigation, generally following a regular schedule of 5-mm events every 6–7 days, resulting in a seasonal average of 643 mm over a single agricultural season.

2.3.1. Satellite data

Satellite data from Sentinel 2 at the spatial resolution of 10 m are used to obtain vegetation data. All images have been atmospherically corrected with Sen2Corr (Sentinel-2 case) software to estimate the bottom of atmosphere reflectance and then, following the procedure implemented in Skokovic (2017) and Skokovic et al. (2017), the vegetation fraction (f_V) is computed as Gutman and Ignatov (1998), while LAI is then calculated as function of f_V and the light extinction coefficient (Choudhury, 1987). Instead, surface albedo was computed as the integration of at-surface reflectance across the shortwave spectrum based on weighting coefficient from Vanino et al. (2018).

2.4. Model initialization and evaluation

For each year, FEST-2 2-EWB has been implemented at the hourly time step of the eddy covariance data. The model requires as input: 1) meteorological variables, such as air temperature and relative humidity, solar radiation, wind velocity and precipitation; 2) irrigation scheduling; 3) soil hydraulic parameters, such as saturated hydraulic conductivity or saturated soil moisture; 4) vegetation parameters, such as leaf area index, vegetation fraction and minimum stomatal resistance ($r_{s, min}$) and a soil resistance.

The water and energy balance parameters have been calibrated and validated using independent variables allowing to verify multiple processes. Eddy covariance (EC) measurements have been used for benchmarking the FEST-2×2-EWB outputs. The footprint of the turbulent fluxes has been considered by using a two-dimensional footprint model (Detto et al., 2006). Thus, modeled LE and H are weighted over the footprint area (Detto et al., 2006).

Data from 2020 have been used for calibration, while from 2019 and 2021 for the validation. In particular, LST and SM data are used for soil parameters calibration, while LE, H, G and Rn are used for the validation step following the procedure developed by Corbari and Mancini (2014).

The model is initialized by assigning literature-suggested values to the different soil parameters based to the soil texture definition, and then modified during the calibration process. The parameter values are always kept within their physical ranges for each soil class (Rawls and Brakensiek, 1985).

FEST-EWB and FEST-2-EWB models were additionally run to be compared with FEST-2×2-EWB. The original model encompasses a

Fig. 2. The walnut trees field location, with the installed eddy covariance station (upper row). The pear tree field location, with the eddy covariance station and the drip irrigation system in place (lower row).

single water and energy balance, looking for the LST that closes pixel-wise the energy balance. The double-source version of the model, although requiring the same amount of input data, assumes that each pixel can be split into a vegetated and a non-vegetated fraction, according to its vegetation fraction parameter, and solves a double energy balance providing two separate land surface temperature as well as ET for the bare soil and crop parts. This improvement may result crucial in analyzing heterogeneous agricultural areas such as those of fruit tree crops, where arboreal canopy is interspersed with bare soil or low-cut grass land cover.

Additionally, the accuracy of the evapotranspiration partitioning algorithm in the FEST-2×2-EWB model has been evaluated in comparison to the underlying water use efficiency (uWUE) method (Zhou et al., 2016) applied to the eddy covariance measurements. The uWUE method allows to partition the observed latent heat flux into transpiration and evapotranspiration relying on VPD, ET and the gross primary production (as measured from the EC station). Following the Zhou et al. (2016) methodology the T/ET ratio is computed as the ratio of an annual potential uWUE for the conditions with the highest GPP gain to water loss and the apparent uWUE for each day of measure. The method accuracy has been analyzed against sap flow data with a RMSE between 0.28 and 0.67 mm/day (Nelson, 2020).

Mean absolute error (MAE), the root mean square error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) are used to verify the model robustness, and are computed as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |S_i - M_i|}{n} \quad (19)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - M_i)^2}{n}} \quad (20)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - M_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \bar{M})^2} \quad (21)$$

where S_i is the i -th simulated variable, M_i is the i -th measured variable, \bar{M} the mean measured variable, n the sample size.

3. Results

3.1. FEST-2×2-EWB calibration and validation

For the walnuts case study, during all the three years (either during calibration and validation), hourly FEST-2×2-EWB estimates correlated well with observed energy fluxes over the whole season from April to September (Fig. 3, Table 2), with R^2 ranging from 0.94 of the net radiation to 0.63 of the sensible heat fluxes, while RMSE is of about 60 W m⁻² for the energy fluxes. In Fig. 4 the simulated fluxes are plotted even when there are not measured data available, making errors seem bigger than they actually are.

Net radiation is represented with good accuracy, as the RMSE is around 61 W m⁻² and all the years obtain similar outcomes, even though the FEST-2×2-EWB is unable to simulate some highest values observations. The RMSE of LE_{FEST-2×2-EWB} ranged between 65 and 69 W m⁻² over the years, showing similarly good results for both calibration and validation years. During May 2020 and June 2021, the simulated LE is slightly overestimated, followed by a period of underestimation coincidental with the hottest days of the years. H_{FEST-2×2-EWB} was slightly overestimated during all the years analyzed, particularly all along 2020, with a RMSE of 73 W m⁻² for the calibration year (2020) and 48 W m⁻² for the validation years (2019 and 2021). For the year 2020, soil heat flux was well represented by the model, with a RMSE of 23 W m⁻² and R^2 of 0.77, while during 2019 and 2021 it was reproduced in disagreement with the measured data due to the representativeness problem of this flux (Kustas et al., 2019).

The model showed a good capability in representing the ground observed LST (Fig. 4), obtaining similar results for all the years, with R^2 around 0.95 and the RMSE ranging from 1.8° to 2.1°C.

The subdivision between surface and deep layer permits to represent properly the soil moisture, obtaining a RMSE of 0.026 and 0.081 (-), respectively. Considering the three years studied, with the exception for the spring months of the year 2020, the trend and dynamics in the surface layer are well reproduced by the FEST-2×2-EWB. Similarly, in the deep layer, there's a good representation of the soil moisture trend either for the years 2019 and 2021.

For the pear trees case study, similar results are obtained (Fig. 3 and Table 2). Error statistics are quite contained, in particular for net radiation and latent heat flux, with RMSE statistics of 28.3 and 54.3 W m⁻² and high R^2 values of 0.98 and 0.85, respectively. Similar statistics are also obtained for sensible heat flux, indicating a good model agreement. All energy fluxes estimates from the FEST-2×2-EWB model, particularly the turbulent ones (sensible and latent heat), show a slight underestimation of the measurements, which is the result of different underestimation and overestimation phases during vegetation growth.

The representation of soil moisture value is better for the deeper layer, as the shallower soil moisture presents an increase between July and August that is poorly reproduced by the model. This might be due to the missing information of soil moisture and irrigation which occurred for a fault in the station recording system.

Finally, the model successfully captured the range of ground-observed LST, with positive error statistics and good representation of monthly dynamics.

3.2. Comparison among models

The FEST-EWB, FEST-EWB-2layers, FEST-2EWB and FEST-2×2-EWB models' performances are evaluated for the different water and energy fluxes in the walnut trees crops, as scatterplots of hourly differences between observed and simulated estimates for walnuts fields for the three years of analysis (Fig. 4).

Mean biases for the sensible heat flux from FEST-2×2-EWB in respect to EC data are quite low (14 W m⁻²). The results from FEST-EWB and FEST-EWB-2layers are quite similar with bias errors of about 12 and 19 W m⁻². Similarly, LE bias from FEST-2×2-EWB is the lowest one, with an average value of 4.64 W m⁻². Instead, the results from FEST-EWB are obtained with a mean bias of 13.98 W m⁻², while from FEST-EWB-2layers the mean bias is equal to 8.41 W m⁻².

LST estimates are similarly improved by the FEST-2×2-EWB model with a lower bias (-0.74 °C in respect to both the FEST-EWB (-1.65 °C) and the FEST-EWB-2layers (-1.76 °C) models.

Also the soil moisture dynamic modeled by FEST-2X2-EWB is considerably improved, especially the deep layer, in respect to both the other models. The average mean biases for the superficial layer are equal to -0.0053 (-) for FEST-2X2-EWB and -0.0136 (-) for FEST-EWB-2layers. As well for the deep layer the biases show a decrease from the FEST-EWB-2layers (-0.1025) to the FEST-2×2-EWB (-0.0516), although the lowest value is the FEST-EWB one (-0.0341), which however accounts for a single layer.

No dependency on the seasonal vegetation dynamic and meteorological variability seems to be present on the models' errors. Higher errors are obtained at higher latent heat flux values (e.g. higher available energy), while no dependency is visible with the vapor pressure deficit (VPD). Similarly, during the three years of analysis, the biases between modeled and observed variables are constant.

A similar analysis has been performed over the pear trees field, where the comparison has been established between FEST-EWB and FEST-2×2-EWB simulations (data not shown). Improvements are obtained across all energy fluxes, with decreasing RMSE values (-14 W m⁻² for net radiation, -5 W m⁻² for LE and -10 W m⁻² for H) and a better representation of the turbulent fluxes dynamic. In terms of surface temperature, a good improvement has been obtained in the double

Fig. 3. Hourly observed and FEST-2x2-EWB estimates for the three years of analysis for the walnut trees field and for the pear trees field: from the top panel the net radiation (Rn), latent heat flux (LE), sensible heat flux (H), superficial and deep soil moistures, land surface temperature (LST).

Table 2

Statistical indexes of the FEST-2×2-EWB model for the energy and water fluxes: net radiation (Rn), latent (LE) and sensible (H) heat fluxes, land surface temperature (LST), shallow (SM sup) and deep (SM dep) soil moisture. The statistical indexes are: the root mean square error (RMSE), the slope of the linear regression (angular coeff.), the correlation coefficient (R²) and the mean absolute error (MAE).

	Walnut trees field				Pear trees field			
	RMSE	Angular coeff.	R ²	MAE	RMSE	Angular coeff.	R ²	MAE
Rn (W/m ²)	61.0	0.88	0.94	45.7	28.3	0.93	0.98	25.9
LE(W/m ²)	66.3	0.89	0.73	46.0	54.3	0.87	0.85	42.1
H(W/m ²)	56.7	1.04	0.63	40.7	48.9	0.85	0.68	37.0
LST (°C)	2.02	1.05	0.95	1.70	2.45	1.05	0.93	2.09
SM sup (-)	0.03	0.89	0.78	0.02	0.03	1.00	0.24	0.03
SM dep (-)	0.08	0.90	0.85	0.08	0.02	1.11	0.51	0.04

Fig. 4. Scatterplots of hourly differences between observed and simulated estimates (FEST-EWB, FEST-EWB-2layers, FEST-2EWB and FEST-2×2-EWB models) for the walnuts trees field in the three years of analysis: from the top panel, latent heat flux (LE), sensible heat flux (H), land surface temperature (LST), superficial and depth soil moistures, at varying vapor pressure deficit (VPD).

comparison with both radiometric and infrared temperatures (obtained by inverting upwelling longwave radiation from the radiometer and from the infrared thermal sensors, respectively). FEST-2×2-EWB manages to represent both temperatures using the appropriate surface temperature: the global RET against the radiometric temperature and the dedicated crop temperature for the infrared sensor retrieval. While, on the other hand, FEST-EWB struggles to obtain good estimations when compared against both temperatures. Finally, the use of a two-layered reference soil volume allows to follow the two different dynamics of soil moisture.

3.3. Flux partitioning comparison

The ability of FEST-2x2-EWB in reproducing the inter-pixel heterogeneity of the different fluxes is firstly analyzed, showing the contribution of the partitioned fluxes to the total ones, as examples for the walnuts field (2020) and the pear field (2022). Latent heat, sensible heat and surface temperature are shown, all provided both globally and in terms of soil and crop components (Fig. 5). Till the beginning of April, the walnut trees are dormant and completely without leaves, while the interrow grass is green and vigorous. H is thus predominant on LE, with the soil component of H being higher than the crop component. The soil component of LST is almost equal to the total LST. Then, from late April till June there is a quick growth of trees canopy. Instead, starting from

Fig. 4. (continued).

July to August the grass becomes dry and slightly yellow, due to the lack of rain and irrigation, which is applied with a localized drip irrigation system directly to the trees. Thus, LE becomes predominant on H, with the crop component of LE being almost equal to the total LE. The total LST is also congruently equal to the crop LST. On the other hand, the monitoring of the pear tree started in late May, when leaves were already densely present in the tree canopy. This means that the balances between the soil and crop components of all variables are mostly unchanged along the whole observation period. In comparison with the walnut field, the pear trees reach a much lower canopy density (around 2 m² m⁻²), meaning that the soil contribution stays non-negligible during the whole season.

The temporal evolution of the T/ET ratio from FEST-2x2-EWB

model is then compared to the T/ET from EC data in respect to the LAI dynamic for the years 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 6). These T/ET behaviours are highly seasonal with the vegetation dynamic inducing a large difference to the ET components contributions. The T/ET ratio is linearly correlated with LAI dynamic.

The ratio from FEST-2x2-EWB model has a low daily variability, while EC data are more oscillating across different days. In this, it appears that the disaggregated transpiration data is highly sensible to meteorological oscillations during the day, whereas the model is more strongly influenced by the overall vegetation dynamic. However, the two T/ET estimates are quite in accordance between each other. The same plot is shown for the pear tree field, where the different phyto-biological character of the plants shows lower LAI values and, in general,

Fig. 5. Total latent (LE) and sensible (H) heat fluxes and land surface temperature (LST), along with the soil and crop components of each variable for both the walnut and pear trees fields.

Fig. 6. Temporal evolution of the transpiration to evapotranspiration (T/ET) ratio from FEST-2X2-EWB model and from EC (T/ET eddy) data in respect to the LAI dynamic for the walnut trees' field in the years 2020 and 2021 and for the pear trees field during 2022.

a more stable dynamic during the observation period (which starts in May, neglecting the development during March and April seen for the walnuts). Overall, the T/ET dynamic seen from the eddy-covariance station is much more unstable and difficult to follow, and presents a wide range of values between the physical constraints of 0 and 1. Nonetheless, looking at the trends in Fig. 6, in late August a progression can be seen, reflected in the growing LAI value, followed by a sharp

decrease around the start of September, well-interpreted by the model.

Similar parallels between modelled T/ET and LAI have been found by Kustas et al. (2019), who employed the TSEB model to determine T/ET and found a medium-high correlation ($r = 0.68$). On the same data, the application of the FEST-2-EWB (Paciolla et al., 2023) has yielded higher correlations ($r = 0.90$), similarly to what has been found here as shown in Fig. 7. This difference can be explained with the

Fig. 7. Scatterplots between daily latent heat (LE) estimates from FEST-2X2-EWB and measurements from EC (eddy): total latent heat (LE), crop transpiration (LE_c), soil evaporation (LE_s) for the available dataset of the walnut (left) and pear (right) fields. Statistical indices are also reported: the slope of the linear regression (m), the correlation coefficient R², and the root mean square error (RMSE).

internal structure of the two models. The transpiration from TSEB is dependent, other than on LAI, also on green vegetation fraction (f_g); in particular in the vegetation senescence period, this parameter may play an important role, smoothing out the relevance of LAI. On the other hand, f_g is not featured within FEST-EWB and its extensions.

The daily LE estimates from FEST-2X2-EWB are finally compared to the LE from eddy station estimates from the uWUE method (Fig. 7), reporting a slight underestimation for the walnut field, with RMSE of 30.4 W m⁻² and a R² = 0.63 and a high slope of linear regression of 0.94. Daily LE_c from FEST-2X2-EWB is also well correlated with LE_c from EC

with RMSE of 30.4 W m⁻². A lower correlation value is found for LE_s, but with a low RMSE being the LE_s absolute values quite low. On the right-hand side of the Figure, the same analysis is carried out for the pear field, which shows similar results for the overall latent heat (relatively low RMSE and medium data dispersion) and a moderate drop in performance for the transpiration data, with more dispersed data (R² = 0.38) that nonetheless provide a lower RMSE. The distribution of the evaporation datapoints is similar to that seen for the walnut field, with a large data dispersion.

Fig. 8. Maps for the walnut field: modeled total latent heat flux (LE_{total}) and its soil (LE_s) and crop (LE_c) components, modeled and satellite Landsat8 LST at 11:00 for the 4 August 2019; Sentinel2 LAI for 30 July 2019.

3.4. Spatial variability

To better understand the infield spatial variability, maps at 10 m of spatial resolution from the FEST-2X2-EWB model of total evapotranspiration and of the soil and crop components are analyzed, together with land surface temperature and vegetation leaf area index. In fact, in Fig. 8 as example, the results are shown for the date of 4 August 2019, as a date representative of a summer day with high peak radiation (752 W m^{-2}) and temperature ($28.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and low air humidity (43%) at 12:00 am with a fully developed vegetation. However, as clearly visible in the southern east part of the field the LAI reaches values of 3.5 (4.5 maximum) while in the other parts a mean value of 2.5. This behavior is reflected in the variability of the LST both from the model and the LANDSAT images, with lower values in the central to southern east part than in the surrounding pixels with a difference that reaches $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The original satellite spatial resolution is equal to 100 m not allowing to detect the ground patches, as the roads or the inter trees rows differences.

In turn, the crop and temperature spatial variability is reflected into the total LE flux and especially into LE_c , with higher values in the southern east part and lower ones in the other field pixels.

The spatial variability of evapotranspiration at 10 m of spatial resolution is also analyzed along the whole 2021 season to identify the areas which differ in crop water use. Thus, maps of total monthly ET are computed (Fig. 9). As expected June and July are the months with the highest ET values, up to 125 mm/month (around 4 mm/day), while April has the minimum measured value (44 W m^{-2}) which is linked to the missing of leaves on the trees. If we then look at the spatial variability of the ET flux a higher standard deviation is detected during June and August (3.4 mm/month) while a lower one in April.

In general, this variability within the walnut trees field is higher than the model errors with respect to the observed data. Moreover, the model is able to capture not only the temporal variability of the evapotranspiration dynamic but also its spatial distribution which is not distinguishable from local eddy covariance measurements alone. This spatial variability might be due to different soil texture within the field and irrigation management.

3.5. Optimized irrigation volumes

The calibrated and validated FEST-2X2-EWB model is finally used to

optimize irrigation management at field scale and it is compared with the observed farmer irrigation management. The observed irrigation volumes are used to run both the FEST-2X2-EWB and the FEST-EWB2layers models.

For the walnut field, in Fig. 10, the water balance fluxes obtained from the four configurations are compared (irrigation, evapotranspiration, and drainage), adding also the rainfall, for the years 2020 and 2021. In the year 2020, a substantial decrease of irrigation volume is found between the observed values and the one obtained from the FEST-2X2-EWB model with the optimization strategy, with a water saving of about 210 mm in a season. Applying the same strategy to the FEST-EWB2layers model, a lower saving of irrigation water is found (150 mm). This is explainable by the two models' parametrizations and equations, with the FEST-2X2-EWB allowing to compute directly the crop transpiration on which irrigation is dependent, whereas the FEST-EWB2layers model computes only the total evapotranspiration flux. The total ET is slightly larger than T, implying higher irrigation volumes needed. For both models, similar values of ET (T) between the two simulation configurations (e.g., modelled with observed irrigations and with the optimized ones) are obtained. An important decrease in the drainage flux is found from the observed irrigation configuration to optimized irrigation management using both models with a larger decrease of FEST-2X2-EWB.

During the year 2021, similar considerations could be made even though with less rainfall. In total about 160 mm of irrigation water could have been saved during the season if the optimized strategy would have been implemented according to FEST-2X2-EWB, while about 110 mm according to FEST-EWB2layers. This is strictly related to the possibility of managing irrigation directly with crop transpiration and not with the total ET.

In Fig. 11, the same analysis is performed over the pear tree field for year 2022. The deeper soil moisture is kept between the two bounds of field capacity (FC) and stress threshold, allowing to reduce the irrigation events (only 7 from the real-life 19) and total volume (roughly 460 mm , depending on the models, from the real-life 570 mm). This allowed percolation losses to be cut down to less than 10 mm , from the $80\text{--}90 \text{ mm}$ of the real-life scenario. In the lower row of the Figure, the preservation of the global ET volume is visible.

Fig. 9. monthly total ET fluxes (ETcum) estimated by the FEST-2X2-EWB model during the 2021 season in the walnut trees field.

Fig. 10. (upper row) Soil moisture dynamics both shallow (Shal.) and deep for the observed (Obs.) and SIM scenarios in respect to field capacity, wilting point and the soil moisture stress threshold over the walnut tree field for the example year 2020 and (lower row) comparison of cumulated water fluxes (rainfall, irrigation, ET, transpiration, percolation) for the observed and SIM scenarios, employing the FEST-EWB2layers and FEST-2X2-EWB models, for the years 2020 and 2021.

3.5.1. Water indicators

The water indicators described in Section 2.2 are employed to quantify the performance of the optimized irrigation strategy using only the FEST-2X2-EWB model, which has been demonstrated to be the one able to more accurately predict the dynamic of the water and energy fluxes in both case studies (Fig. 12). The WpC indicator remains almost constant when shifting from the traditional irrigation to the optimal one, as the evapotranspiration, and thus plant activity, is mostly unaffected by the shift. On the other hand, the WpI increases considerably with the optimization of the irrigation, as no water stress is induced (meaning no reduction in plant activity and production) when the optimized irrigation is applied. A similar response is then provided by both the Percolation Deficit and the Irrigation Efficiency indices, with higher values with the optimized strategy as opposed to the traditional management.

4. Discussion

The developed model approach is based on the combination of a two layers soil scheme and a time continuous two source energy balance scheme, and has allowed improving the estimates of the water and energy fluxes for fruit trees fields in central Italy in respect to previous model versions based on single soil layer and/or single source energy balance schemes.

As demonstrated by Paciolla et al. (2023), a single soil layer and single source energy balance model, as the original FEST-EWB model (Corbari et al., 2011), might produce high errors when applied to

heterogeneous cover crops, like vineyards. This consideration was already highlighted by Norman et al. (1995) who developed the first two-sources energy balance model, TSEB, based on the use of satellite land surface temperature as driving information for partitioning the ET flux for the crop and soil components. The representation of the ET modeling in heterogeneous crops has been also recently improved by Burchard-Levine et al. (2022) including also a third layer for soil and grass besides trees (3SEB). Many different models have been developed to simulate the partitioned fluxes either based on satellite LST data, as Khan et al. (2021) who developed a two-source version of the single-source SEBS model (Su, 2002) based on LAI variability, or Cui and Jia (2021) based on a soil moisture data assimilation scheme into a water balance model, or again Bhattarai et al. (2022) based on the combination of visible and SWIR satellite data employing the Shuttleworth and Wallace equation for ET computation.

The FEST-2X2-EWB scheme allows to improve this representation of the TSEB and the 3SEB models thanks to: 1) overcome the issue of satellite data availability (limited by clouds and satellite revisit time), because unlike most models, which require LST as an input, FEST-EWB computes LST as an internal variable and has physically-based, non-residual formulations for the components of the energy balance (Corbari et al., 2011); 2) its ability to model the soil moisture dynamic continuously in time for different soil layers.

Besides providing an estimate of the total fluxes, the FEST-2X2-EWB scheme has been demonstrated to reproduce the soil and vegetation components of the energy fluxes in respect to eddy covariance

Fig. 11. (upper row) Soil moisture dynamics both shallow (Shal.) and deep for the observed (Obs.) and SIM scenarios in respect to field capacity, wilting point and the soil moisture stress threshold over the pear tree field and (lower row) comparison of cumulated water fluxes (rainfall, irrigation, ET, transpiration, percolation) for the observed and SIM scenarios, employing the FEST-EWB and FEST-2X2-EWB models.

partitioned fluxes.

Recently, the study of the evapotranspiration components has gained new attention due to the increasing importance of water uses in irrigated agriculture, while remaining still an open problem due to the complex interaction between the soil dynamic, crop and meteorological conditions. Thus, the T/ET ratio can vary from 30% to 90% (Anderson et al., 2017; Fisher et al., 2017; Nelson et al., 2020; Perez-Priego et al., 2018).

In this work, the most influencing variables have been found to be the water availability and vegetation dynamic. In fact, the availability of water, which is water-limited areas, is mainly distributed with irrigation which is mainly provided only to the crops (e.g. drip irrigation), enhancing the differences between T and E. Moreover, fruit trees have usually long roots able to absorb deeper soil water, while bare soil or grass have a quicker evapotranspiration response to the rapid dynamic of the superficial soil moisture.

The validation of the components of evapotranspiration is most of the time a complex issue due to the limitations or scarcity of transpiration data. For example, sap flow measurements provide transpiration measure, but are very local related to a single tree (Smith and Allen, 1996) needing to be scaled up to the whole field level possibly leading to uncertainties related to the crop conditions variability (Roupsard et al.,

2006; Wilson et al., 2001). Moreover, some types of trees may implement protective measures against the forks in the trunk leading to erroneous measurements (Rienth and Scholasch, 2019).

Thus, the estimates of the ET components from the FEST-2X2-EWB model are verified against partitioned fluxes from eddy covariance data, guaranteeing low RMSE values. Transpiration data from eddy covariance station are actually derived data using a modeling scheme based on correlations between data of water vapor and CO₂ (Zhou et al., 2016), which has been proved to provide accurate transpiration estimates. However, especially in arid sites where evaporation plays a role, the relationship with atmospheric conditions in terms of vapor pressure deficit and soil moisture should be also considered (Scott and Biederman, 2017).

Finally, the calibrated FEST-2X2-EWB has been applied implementing an optimized irrigation strategy based on soil moisture thresholds, which could improve the current irrigation practice in the operative water management of the farm (Corbari and Mancini, 2022). In fact, in comparison to the observed farmer irrigation management, a smaller irrigation volume is obtained and also in terms of the number of irrigations (e.g. less man work needed and less energy). Moreover, a higher water saving is observable when using the two-sources version

Fig. 12. Water indicators (WPC, WPI, Percolation Deficit, Irrigation Efficiency) compared between observed and SIM scenarios for the walnut trees field (WAL20 (e.g. walnut trees for the year 2020) and WAL21 (e.g. walnut trees for the year 2021)) and pear trees field (PEA22 (e.g. pear trees for the year 2022)).

(FEST-2X2-EWB) in respect to the single source, due to fact that in the first case the irrigation is triggered only on T and not the total ET which is slightly bigger.

The implemented strategy also differs from the common employed methods which are usually based on keeping the evapotranspiration close to potential using remote sensing crop parameters (e.g., the crop coefficient) (D'Urso, 2010; Vuolo et al., 2015; Calera Belmonte et al., 2017), or based on soil stress thresholds with traditional water balance schemes (Allen et al., 1998).

The FEST-2X2-EWB estimates of evapotranspiration maps at 10 m of spatial resolution have been also analyzed allowing to identify the areas which differ in crop water use. This might further increase the potential of the optimized irrigation differentiating for different areas (e.g. variable rate irrigation) leading to a global increase in water use efficiency (Gobbo et al., 2019; Liakos et al., 2015).

A possible limitation to the newly developed version of the model might be related to the definition of the ground heat flux, where in this FEST-2X2-EWB model version we've opted to treat the canopy and the underlying soil surface as a unified element within the energy balance framework, symbolized by a singular radiative temperature. This approach involves approximations of certain energy exchange processes, including the soil heat flux (Lhomme et al., 2012; Norman et al., 1995).

Moreover, the consideration of a different inter-rows coverage allowing to distinguish between bare soil or grass cover crop, could further enhance the model in the processes representation, as the idea developed in the remotely-sensed based three-source model by Burchard-Levine et al. (2022).

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the development of a double two-sources energy-water balance model (FEST-2×2-EWB) based on the decoupling of both water and energy fluxes between the bare soil or grass interrow and the trees rows. This novel parameterization approach enables the differentiation of water uptake from the root zone, which varies between tall trees and grass, considering the dynamics of water in the soil superficial and deep layers. The model allows to provide

continuous in time estimates of evapotranspiration and soil moisture. The model simulations encompassed two irrigated trees fields in the North of Italy, a walnut trees field from 2019 to 2021 and a pear trees field, for the year 2022.

Notably, FEST-2×2-EWB demonstrated a high level of accuracy with root-mean-square-error (RMSE) of about 55 W m^{-2} and a bias of about 40 W m^{-2} for hourly latent and sensible heat fluxes when compared to the eddy covariance stations located in the fields, while a RMSE of $2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (bias of $1.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for LST and of 0.04 for SM, showing a slight improvement over the original FEST-EWB model. The modeled ratio of transpiration to ET (T/ET) was largely consistent with an eddy covariance (EC)-based approach, albeit slightly overestimated.

This offers the potential to enhance fruits trees water stress analyzes by distinguishing crop transpiration, thereby assisting irrigation managers in water resources management. In fact, the application of an irrigation optimization strategy with this new model, allowed to demonstrate its potentiality in water saving (about 90 mm in a year) in respect to farmers applied irrigation, and with a difference of about 60 mm between using the double two-sources model and single source one.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization: Chiara Corbari (CC); Data curation: CC; Formal analysis: CC, Nicola Paciolla (NP), Greta Rossi (GR); Funding acquisition: Marco Mancini (MM), CC; Investigation: CC, NP, GR; Methodology: CC, NP; Project administration: MM; Resources: CC, NP, GR; Software: CC, NP; Supervision: CC, MM; Validation: CC, NP, GR; Visualization: CC, NP; Writing (original draft): CC, NP.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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